

FONT AS A MEANS OF VISUAL BRAND IDENTIFICATION

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Abstract. Fonts are an important element of a brand's visual identity, emphasising its uniqueness and helping to establish an emotional connection with consumers. The right choice of typographics can not only attract attention, but also influence the perception of brand values, the formation of associations and emotional approaches towards it. This paper analyses how fonts help to emphasise brand uniqueness, create positive associations and improve communication efficiency. Particular attention is paid to the impact of typographics on consumers' emotional perception and the importance of font flexibility in the context of modern digital technologies. Using The Examples of Coca-Cola, Google and Nike, the author demonstrates that font area powerful branding tool that ensures long-term popularity and recognition.

Keywords: branding, fonts, visual identity, design, typographics, marketing.

Modern brands face intense competition, which makes it important to create a strong and effective visual identity. Typographics, especially the choice of fonts, is becoming an important part of this process. A font not only facilitates transferring of information, but also shapes the emotional perception of a brand. For example, the Coca-Cola font has become synonymous with retro style and evokes associations with nostalgia and tradition (Henderson, et al., 2004).

The choice of font has an important impact on the perception of a brand and its messages to the audience. A font may emphasize a sense of seriousness, warmth, modernity, or other emotions. For example, serif fonts reflect a traditional style that has evolved over centuries. Their classic look is associated with trust and heritage, making them an ideal choice for creating a stable and authoritative brand image. In turn, sans serif fonts are often associated with novelties and minimalism. Their lack of decorative elements ensures high readability and eases perception, making them a great option for projects focused on functionality. This simplicity makes serif fonts look modern, clean, and attractive.

When it comes to handwritten fonts, they are ideal for creating intricate and

detailed logos, as they are more elegant than serif fonts. They are usually associated with creativity due to their calligraphic structure, which gives them a sophisticated look. This style adds personality to the design and helps to connect emotionally with the audience. However, it is important to ensure their readability so that the text is easily understood. Psychologically, handwritten fonts are versatile: they can convey both playfulness and tradition. Due to their creative nature, they are ideal for brands that want to emphasize their creativity, particularly in the fashion, food, and children's industry.

Slab Serif combines the features of serif and sans serif fonts and features massive tile-like serifs. They create an impression of strength, confidence, and reliability. This style is often used in contexts that are associated with strength and stability, such as on factory stamps or tools. Slab Serifs are becoming the choice of companies willing to express their innovation and modernity. They are popular among tech brands that demonstrate confidence and willingness to break stereotypes. Due to their structure, these fonts are perfectly readable at any scale, making them versatile in use (Dissidend, 2024).

Google uses the Product Sans font in its identity, which embodies openness, simplicity, and a modern approach. In turn, Nike chose Futura Bold, which conveys confidence, energy, and dynamics. These examples show how carefully selected typography helps brands create a powerful visual image that reflects their core values (Henderson, et al., 2004).

Fonts that have unique characteristics give a brand the opportunity to stand out from the competition and stick in the minds of consumers. For example, decorative fonts serve as a tool for creative expression, as they are often created specifically for a brand. Each of these fonts has its own personality, which makes them versatile for conveying specific emotions. This is especially important for branding. However, they are rarely used in long-form texts - they are mostly used to create logos, advertising materials, and visual elements where their creative properties can be maximized. For example, the Disney font is associated with fairytales and playfulness. This level of recognition becomes even more important in today's digital world, where brands are fighting for consumer attention (Campbell, et al., 2023).

Typographics have a significant impact on the emotional background of consumers. Rounded fonts, like Google's, evoke associations with friendliness and positive emotions, while fonts with sharp lines, like Adidas', convey strength and energy. The choice of font should be aligned with the brand's values and overall communication style. For example, strict fonts are appropriate for formal institutions to emphasize authority, while more playful options are suitable for brands that target a young audience or children, such as Lego (American Marketing Association, 2023).

Modern digital technologies have greatly expanded the possibilities for using fonts, making them versatile across platforms. For example, Netflix has developed its own Netflix Sans font, which meets the specific requirements of their digital products while reducing licensing costs. Airbnb has taken a similar approach, using the Airbnb

Cereal font to maintain its brand integrity across all digital platforms (Henderson, et., al., 2004).

Typography not only supports visual identity, but also contributes to brand recognition. For example, the Coca-Cola font is so distinctive that it can be recognized even without a logo (Yadav, et. al., 2014).

Innovative approaches open up new horizons for branding. Dynamic fonts, for example, allow a brand to adapt to different cultural contexts and conditions. Global brands such as Apple use typographics that remain recognizable all around the world, while taking into account language and regional specialties.

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